

HOSPITALITY STUDENTS WORKING INTENTION IN THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY: A CASE STUDY IN BERJAYA UNIVERSITY COLLEGE MALAYSIA

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ABSTRACT

Hospitality industry has become one of the major industries in the nation economy. It makes hospitality industry demand on the professional workers, which includes hospitality students as they are the ideal workers for hospitality industry. Thus, it is important to know the working intention of hospitality students towards hospitality students in order to attract them working in hospitality industry. The study is aimed to understand the working intention of hospitality students towards hospitality industry. The study is also determined on whether pay and benefits, parental influence, career development and personal interest affect hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry. Besides, the correlation test shows that all the independent variables (pay and benefits, parental influence, career development and personal interest) are having relationship with dependent variable variables (hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry). Also, the regression test has shown that all the independent variables (pay and benefits, parental influence, career development and personal interest) affect dependent variables (hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry). The findings may able to help hospitality employers and further researchers to refer to understand student intention towards working in hospitality industry.

Keywords: *Hospitality industry, hospitality student, working intention.*

INTRODUCTION

The research is being conducted to understand the working intention of hospitality student towards hospitality industry. Also, this research is aim to understand the impact of the independent variables include pay and benefits, parental influence and career development towards the dependent variables which is hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry. Kuala Lumpur is the capital of Malaysia and it is located at the West of Malaysia. The main hub of Kuala Lumpur, Golden Triangle is even the place that involve of greater development of hospitality industry.

This research is focusing on Berjaya University College; it is a private university that located in the golden triangle of the vibrant city of Kuala Lumpur since 2009 (Come Study Abroad at Berjaya UC n.d.). Currently, Berjaya University College offers more than 20 different courses which are mainly from the four faculty includes Faculty of Hospitality and Tourism, Faculty of Business, Faculty of Culinary Arts and Faculty of Liberty Arts. In the School of Hospitality, the courses that available in Berjaya University College includes Foundation in Hospitality, Diploma in Hotel Management, Bachelor of Hospitality Management (Hons) and Wine & Spirit Education Trust (WSET).

Hospitality industry is a broad group of businesses that provide service to the customers. It is an important topic that should be determined in order to understand the hospitality student's intention towards working in hospitality industry after their graduation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Hospitality Students' Working Intention towards Hospitality Industry

Intention is subjective judgments about how a person will behave in future and it usually serves as a dependent variable in many service research and satisfaction models G Selvanayagam (2020). According to Walsh, Chang and Tse (2015), they had studied that only about half of the graduates in the research may apply their first job in hospitality industry. The researchers also claimed that the students with higher emotional intelligence and service oriented were more willing to join hospitality industry as their personal traits are suitable for hospitality industry. This is because hospitality industry's bad image on offering low status and low paying job has vanished the hospitality students' working intention towards hospitality industry. The researchers found that the hospitality students in Hong Kong, Korea and Taiwan has the intention to work in hospitality industry after graduation because of the existence of job opportunities. However, Hong Kong students responded negatively on the dissatisfied and unstable working environment in hospitality industry while Korean and Taiwan students has positive response towards working in hospitality industry. There are only small number of students choose to work in hospitality industry after graduated in China as large number of students are choosing to work in other industry after graduated. The result showed that students have low commitment to the hospitality industry and the desire to work in hospitality industry were even decreased after direct interaction with workplaces. Due to this, the researchers found that many students were not planning to join hospitality industry. In Adhoch's (2019) study, the researcher found that majority of fourth year students agreed that they would work in the hospitality industry after graduation. The researcher found that his respondents felt pride and pleasure while working in hospitality industry. According to Kukreti and Dani (2020) who conducted a research on studying the perception and preferences of hospitality management students towards working in hotel industry, hospitality students have both positive and negative perception and preferences towards working in hotel industry. The study also stated that the different factors can change the perception and preferences of hospitality students towards working in hospitality industry such as the salary, working experience and global prospect.

Pay and Benefits

As stated by Wahab, Rosli and Shahril (2020), pay and benefits is the "total reward system that characterizes the compensation structure. Salary is the payment obligation of employers to the employees as it will affect employees' short term and long-term financial position (Achim, Badrolhisam and Zulkipli 2019). Other than that employee benefit can be defined as any indirect or non-cash compensation paid to an employee. The researcher stated that the financial compensation is the pull factor for students to join hospitality industry and a final year hospitality students will consider of pay while choosing their career path. The low or unsatisfied pay might change the students' decision of working in hospitality industry. The low salary packages offered in hospitality industry is the reason of students' negative attitude to work in hospitality industry. The researchers stated that according to Kusluvan and Kusluvan (2000), pay and benefits have an undesirable perception from the students towards hospitality industry. Pay and benefits will moderately affect the students' intention to work in hospitality industry (Wahab, Rosli and Shahril 2020). As mentioned by Dwivedi (2018), the result of the study showed that the students were less concerned on pay compared to others elements such as growth opportunity and as stated by Kukreti and Dani (2020), pay can affect the perception and preferences of hospitality students towards working in hospitality industry. As stated by Qiu, Dooley and Palkar (2017), parent affect is one of the factors that affecting the career choice of hotel management major students. The interesting part is male students is having higher score than female students on parental influence towards their career path decision (Qiu, Dooley and Palkar 2017).

Parental Influence

According to Atef and Balushi (2017), youngsters will be affected by people surrounding them. However, while youngsters have different opinions with their parents, parents can be the barrier of career decision making (Hui, Rashid and Mohammed 2017). According to Bikse et.al (2018), parents can be one of the factors that affect career choice of students. Akosah-Twumasi et.al (2018) who studied the review of other researches on the factors that affect career choice claimed that parental influence is one of the interpersonal factors that affect career choice of youths. Also, Polenova et.al (2018) stated that

parental value and parental pressure can affect students' career choice. Students indicated that parents would give suggestions based on parents' perception on career choice (Polenova et.al 2018). According to Tan and Tay (2019), parents play a crucial role in career decision making. Abdinoor and Ibrahim (2019) stated that parental support is one of the factors that affect career decision as parents have played important role in children's education and career planning. Parents' support and attitude can affect children's making career decision while having career guidance with their children.

Career Development

According to Gyansah and Guantai (2018), career development defined as the management of an individual's growth and progress in his or her career. A well-planned career development may include talent management, performance appraisal, development activities, opportunities for transfer and promotion, and planning and succession. Career development is focused on developing and enriching the human resource in an organization in light of both employees' and organization needs. Rashid and Mohammed (2017) as they stated that students have experience on career development from the training in hospitality industry have change their attitude towards working in hospitality industry. However, they stated that the average promotion opportunities in hospitality industry would vanish the willingness of final year students to join hospitality. Lusby's study (2017) has found that American and Macau students would looking at the promotion opportunities before committing to the tourism and hospitality industry. Career development is one of the key factors that affect one's career decision as the career development is positively affect the career outcomes. The researcher also claimed that the employers in hospitality industry should enhance the career development system in order to attract graduates to join the industry. As identified by El-Houshy (2018), promotion prospect is one of the important factors that most hospitality students will look into while choosing their career.

Personal Interest

Personal interest is one of the most important factors that student would take into account while making career choice. However, lesser student from Hong Kong agreed to join hospitality industry because of personal interest. Nyamwange's (2016) research had studied about how personal interest influence career choice decisions among university students. The researcher also recommended students to choose their career that they are interested in as this could make them work better in their career path. As stated by Ahmed, Sharif and Ahmad (2017), the success of young leaders in their career depends on the alignment of their career choice with their interest. Okojide, Adekeye and Bakare (2018) claimed that personal interest is one of the factors that can affect students' choice of career. Besides, the results in the research by Okojide, Adekeye and Bakare (2018) showed that personal interest has significant influence on making the career choice. As mentioned by Malik, Said and Munap (2018), personal interest is one of the intrinsic factors that can affect students' career choice. The researchers also claimed that if students follow their personal interest on choosing their career, students would be satisfied easier. al (2018) as evidences to show that personal interest is an important factor while people making career choice. al (2015) claimed that personal interest significantly affects the career choice of Chinese students while Atitsogbe et al (2018) claimed that Swiss students' career choice are more influenced by personal interest too.

Research Objectives

1. To understand hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry.
2. To determine the relationship between the independent variables (e.g. Pay and Benefits, Parental Influence, Career Development and Personal Interest) and the dependent variable (e.g. Hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry).
3. To determine whether the independent variables (e.g. Pay and Benefits, Parental Influence, Career Development and Personal Interest) are affecting the dependent variable (e.g. Hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry).

4. To test the respondents' intention towards working in hospitality industry due to the COVID-19 outbreak.

Hypotheses

- Ha1: Pay and benefits affect hospitality students' working intention towards hospitality industry.
Ho1: Pay and benefits do not affect hospitality students' working intention toward hospitality industry.
- Ha2: Parental influence affects hospitality students' working intention towards hospitality industry.
Ho2: Parental influence does not affect hospitality students' working intention towards hospitality industry.
- Ha3: Career development affects hospitality students' working intention towards hospitality industry.
Ho3: Career development does not affect hospitality students' working intention towards hospitality industry.
- Ha4: Personal interest affects hospitality students' working intention towards hospitality industry.
Ho4: Personal interest does not affect hospitality students' working intention towards hospitality industry.

Framework

Figure 1.0: Conceptual Framework Model and proposed model

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher has applied the method of quantitative approach. Quantitative approach is often used as a synonym for any data collection technique such as questionnaire or data analysis procedure such as graphs that generates or uses numerical data. In quantitative approach, the analyst will concentrate on the quantitative facts or data associated with the problem and develop mathematical expressions that describe the objectives, constraints, and other relationships that exist in the circumstances.

Sampling

According to Berjaya University College (2020), the population of students in Berjaya University College is about 1,001 to 10,000 students. According to the latest data provided by the Registry Department of Berjaya University College on Jun 2020, there are 186 hospitality students studying in Berjaya University College included hospitality students from Diploma and Degree. Therefore, the sample size of the study would be the *186 hospitality students*. It is because the research was only focused

on studying the intention of hospitality students from Berjaya University College towards working in hospitality industry.

	Progs	Nov-18	Dec-18	Jan-19	Dec-19	Jan-20	Feb-20	Mar-20	Apr-20	May-20	Jun-20
FHT-SH	BHM	197	197	199	160	148	147	147	147	117	116
	DIHM	142	142	134	87	89	88	87	87	70	70
FHT-ST	BEV	38	38	39	39	35	35	35	35	33	33
	BTT	19	19	19	17	17	15	15	15	15	15
	DEV	74	74	75	58	57	57	57	57	46	46
	DTT	29	29	26	24	22	22	20	20	16	15

(Source: Registry Department, Berjaya University College, 2020)

Figure 2.0: current number of students in Berjaya University College

Purposive sampling was used in this research. According to Paul J. Lavrakas (2008) purposive sample, also referred to as a judgmental or expert sample, is a type of nonprobability sample. The main objective of a purposive sample is to produce a sample that can be logically assumed to be representative of the population. This is often accomplished by applying expert knowledge of the population to select in a non-random manner a sample of elements that represents a cross-section of the population.

Research Instrument

The research was obtained by distributing the questionnaires to the target respondents who are hospitality students that are studying in Berjaya University College. The questionnaire has divided into three section which is Section A, Section B and Section C. In Section A, there are screening questions for respondents to answer in order to make sure they are hospitality students from Berjaya University College. In Section B, there are multiple choice questions about the demographics profile of the respondents which included gender, nationality, races, course of the respondents studying and the year of study. In Section C, the respondents were asked to rate by using a five-point Likert scale from 1= “Strongly disagree” to 5= “Strongly agree” on 5 dimensions: (1) Pay and Benefits, (2) Parental influence, (3) Career Development, (4) Personal Interest and (5) Hospitality students’ intention towards working in hospitality industry.

Data Collection

According to Hussey and Hussey (1997), G Selvanayagam (2020) all research has a primary stage which they must pass through and this include; Defining the research problem, Determining the concept of the research, Collecting the necessary data for the research, Analysing and interpreting the research data, stating the findings and recommendations. Digital questionnaires were distributed through Google questionnaire form and by distributing hardcopies to participants.

Pilot Test

It is important to ensure that the items in the questionnaires are consistent with the construct definition. Since all items that were employed in the current study were established through the adoption of validated instruments by previous researchers, the content validity is established. This is to ensure explicitness with the wording of the measurements and the items are easily understood by the respondents. Any inaccuracies and inadequacies are corrected before the actual field research is conducted, G Selvanayagam (2020). Overall, the alpha scores for all main constructs exceeded the benchmark of 0.70. Rectifications were made based on the feedback of the respondents.

Data Analysis Method

All the data will be analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) after all the data are being collected. In this journal the discussion will be based on the results of Reliability Test, Correlation Analysis and Regression Analysis.

RESULTS

Reliability Test

Pay and Benefits	.804
Parental Influence	.887
Career Development	.811
Personal Interest	.887
students' intention	.951

Figure 3.0: SPSS Reliability Test Results

The reliability statistics for all 30 elements that from the independent variables and dependent variable. As stated in above and the all Variables Reliability Cronbach's Alpha is 0.941, which is more than 0.90. It means that all variables are in the excellent reliability level). It indicates that all the elements from all the variables are reliable and can be used to measure without bias as per figure 3.0 above.

Test of Normality

A total of 30 elements have been analysed through normality test with the 176 sets of valid data., values of 2 standard errors of skewness or more (regardless of sign) are probably skewed to a significant degree; values of 2 standard errors of kurtosis or more (regardless of sign) probably differ from mesokurtic to a significant degree. It means that it has indicated the acceptable range of skewness and kurtosis to show normal distribution is +2 to -2.

By looking into the table below (Table 1.0), the statistic for skewness for all 30 elements were fall between 0.747 to -1.402; while the statistic for kurtosis for all 30 elements were fall between 1.205 to -1.281. As both value of skewness and kurtosis were all in the acceptable range, the data were considered as normally distributed.

Analysis of Correlation

Table 1.0: Correlation Coefficient of All Variables

		IV1	IV2	IV3	IV4	DV
	Pearson Correlation	1	.436**	.734**	.726**	.811**
IV1	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	176	176	176	176	176
	Pearson Correlation	.436**	1	.398**	.241**	.430**
IV2	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.001	.000
	N	176	176	176	176	176
	Pearson Correlation	.734**	.398**	1	.887**	.746**
IV3	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	176	176	176	176	176
	Pearson Correlation	.726**	.241**	.887**	1	.849**
IV4	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.001	.000		.000
	N	176	176	176	176	176
	Pearson Correlation	.811**	.430**	.746**	.849**	1
DV	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	176	176	176	176	176

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

Pearson Correlation Coefficient is being used in the context of linear relationship between independent variables and dependent variable in this study. According to Schober and Boer (2018), Pearson Correlation Coefficient is typically used for normally distributed data. Thus, this study would use Pearson Correlation Coefficient as the data were normally distributed. It is to measure the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables. By looking into Table 4.0, as the probability of all IVs and DV are less than 0.05, it is considered as statistically significant. Thus, the researcher could continue looking into the correlation value of the IVs and DV.

Based on Table 1.0 the correlation (r) value of all IVs and DV are being shown. IV1 which stands for Pay and Benefits obtains a value of 0.811; while IV2 which stands for Parental Influence obtains a value of 0.430. Besides, IV3 which stands for Career Development has a value of 0.746; while IV4 which stands for Personal Interest has a value of 0.849. All independent variables have positive relationship with the dependent variables. IV1 and IV4 with correlation value of 0.811 and 0.849 are fall within the range of 0.80-1.00. Thus, it indicates that IV1 (Pay and Benefits) and IV4 (Personal Interest) have very strong positive relationship with DV (Hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry. Furthermore, IV2 (Parental Influence) with a correlation value of 0.430 indicates

that it has moderate positive relationship with DV (Hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry). Also IV3 (Career Development) has strong positive relationship with DV (Hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry) as the correlation value of 0.746 is fall between 0.60-0.79.

Looking into the coefficient (r) value, IV4 (Personal Interest) has the strongest positive relationship with DV (Hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry), followed by IV1 (Pay and Benefits), IV3 (Career Development) and IV2 (Parental Influence).

Analysis of Regression

Linear Regression is being used by the researcher in this study to analyse the data. Linear regression is being used in the analysis of influence. It is a statistical procedure for calculating the value of a dependent variable from an independent variable. It can measure the association between two variables. By using this method, researcher is able to find that whether the independent variables (Pay and Benefits, Parental Influence, Career Development and Personal Interest) can affect the dependent variables (Hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry).

Table 2.0: Descriptive Statistics for All Variables

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
IV1	176	3.8532	.72050
IV2	176	3.0464	.87227
IV3	176	3.7680	.59495
IV4	176	3.8419	.71764
DV	176	3.6146	.83892
Valid N (listwise)	176		

Model Summary of Regression Analysis and ANOVA

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.918^a	.843	.839	.33639

a. Predictors: (Constant), IV4, IV2, IV1, IV3

Table 6.0 Model Summary of the all independent variables against dependent variable

Table 3.0: ANOVA of All Independent Variables Against Dependent Variable

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	103.811	4	25.953	229.350	.000^b
Residual	19.350	171	.113		
Total	123.161	175			

a. Dependent Variable: DV

b. Predictors: (Constant), IV4, IV2, IV1, IV3

Table 2.0 shows that the correlation coefficient (R) is 0.918 which means that the independent variables (Pay and Benefits, Parental Influence, Career Influence and Personal Influence) have very strong positive relationship against the dependents variable (Hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry). Moreover, the table shows that the value of R square (R^2) is 0.843. It can indicate that there are 84.3% of variation of hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry can be explained by the independent variables which include pay and benefits, parental influence, career development and personal interest. On the other hand, the remaining 15.7% can be explained by other excluded factors. Hence, the other possible factors can be conducted by other researchers in the future in other to understand more about the possible factors that may affect hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry. Not only that, according to Table 3.0 (ANOVA test), the model is considered as statistically significant as the F value is 229.350 at the p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05.

Coefficient Results

Table 4.0: Regression Coefficients of All Independent Variables against Dependent Variable

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.544	.167		-3.251	.001
	IV1	.425	.056	.365	7.546	.000
	IV2	.203	.035	.211	5.854	.000
	IV3	-.525	.103	-.373	-5.112	.000
	IV4	1.010	.084	.864	12.008	.000

Dependent Variable: DV

Table 4.0 is the regression coefficients analysis which conducted to examine that whether the independent variable is significant to predict the dependent variable. The variables above are IV1 (Pay and Benefits), IV2 (Parental Influence), IV3 (Career Development) and IV4 (Personal Interest) and the dependent variable is hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry. The results in Table 4.5.2.1 shows that, the coefficient of IV1 (Pay and Benefits) is $t(7,546) = 0.425$, $p = 0.000$, IV2 (Parental Influence) is $t(5,854) = 0.203$, $p = 0.000$, IV3 (Career Development) is $t(-5,112) = -0.525$, $p = 0.000$ and IV4 (Personal Interest) is $t(12,008) = 1.010$, $p = 0.000$. All significant values of all independent variables are below 0.05, therefore, it indicates that all independent variables (Pay and Benefits, Parental Influence, Career Development and Personal Interest) can predict hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry. It also concluded that all independent variables (Pay and Benefits, Parental Influence, Career Development and Personal Interest) can affect hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry.

The results have been told that hospitality students would considered on pay and benefits and career development before joining hospitality industry. Also, hospitality students would career about their parents' advises and self-interest before making choice of career.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing is to review whether the hypothesis of this study is accepted or rejected.

Hypothesis 1

Ha₁: Pay and benefits affect hospitality students' working intention towards hospitality industry.

Ho₁: Pay and benefits do not affect hospitality students' working intention toward hospitality industry.

According to Table 1, the significant p-value of pay and benefits variable is $p=0.000$, which is lower than 0.05. Thus, the researcher can indicate that in this study, Ha₁ is accepted and Ho₁ is rejected, pay and benefits affect hospitality students' working intention towards hospitality industry.

Hypothesis 2

Ha₂: Parental influence affects hospitality students' working intention towards hospitality industry.

Ho₂: Parental influence does not affect hospitality students' working intention towards hospitality industry.

Looking into Table 1, the significant p-value of parental influence variable is $p=0.000$, which is lesser than 0.05. Thus, the researcher can indicate that in this study, Ho₂ is rejected and Ha₂ is accepted. It indicates that parental influence affects hospitality students' working intention towards hospitality industry.

Hypothesis 3

Ha₃: Career development affects hospitality students' working intention towards hospitality industry.

Ho₃: Career development does not affect hospitality students' working intention towards hospitality industry.

According to Table 1, the significant p-value of career development variable is $p=0.000$, which is lower than 0.05. Thus, the researcher can indicate that in this study, Ha₃ is accepted and Ho₃ is rejected. It means that career development affects hospitality students' working intention towards working in hospitality industry.

Hypothesis 4

Ha₄: Personal interest affects hospitality students' working intention towards hospitality industry.

Ho₄: Personal interest does not affect hospitality students' working intention towards hospitality industry.

Looking into Table 1, the significant p-value of personal interest variable is $p=0.000$, which is lesser than 0.05. Thus, the researcher can indicate that in this study, Ho₄ is rejected and Ha₄ is accepted. It indicates that personal interest affects hospitality students' working intention towards hospitality industry.

In summary, this section has analysed all 176 sets of valid data in order to get the result for this study. From the descriptive analysis, the researcher found that the main respondents of this study were female, Malaysian, Chinese, studying Bachelor of Hospitality Management and in second year of study as those characteristics have largest proportion in the analysis. The reliability test and normality test have shown that the data are reliable and normally distributed. Not only that, the results show that all independent variables (Pay and Benefits, Parental Influence, Career Development and Personal Interest) are having positive relationship with the dependent variable (Hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry) after analysing by Pearson Correlation Coefficient. Furthermore, the results have indicated that all the independent variables can affect the dependents variables after being analysing by Linear Regression. Last but not least, the hypothesis testing has indicated that Ha₁, Ha₂, Ha₃ and Ha₄ has being accepted and Ho₁, Ho₂, Ho₃ and Ho₄ has being rejected.

CONCLUSION

This study aims to understand the working intention of Berjaya University College hospitality students toward hospitality industry. Besides, some recommendations for hospitality employers to attract hospitality students join the hospitality industry for their future career and some suggestions for further researchers to conduct a better research that related to this topic would be provided. The other potential factors that affect students' intention towards working in hospitality industry could be focused for the further researches.

The research consists of four independent variables that included pay and benefits, parental influence, career development and personal interest and one dependent variable which is hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry. Hopefully, this study can help employers of hospitality industry to understand the factor that affecting hospitality students to join hospitality industry. Also, this study might can be a reference for further researcher on the relevant topic in order to understand the deeper and better about the hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry.

The researcher has indicated that lack of professionalism is occurred in hospitality industry while hospitality industry is rising consistently in Malaysia. Thus, it is important to know the factors that affect potential professionalism of hospitality industry, which is hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry. The researcher has conducted the research by analysing 176 sets of responses from the target respondents as valid data. The result of pay and benefits can affect hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry is stick to the result the found by El-Houshy (2018), Wahab, Rosli and Shahril (2020) and Kukreti and Dani (2020) as the researchers have found that pay and benefits can affect students' intention on joining an industry, Also, it is possible that parental influence can affect hospitality students; This is because Qiu, Dooley and Palkar (2017) claimed that parent affect is one of the factors that affecting the career choice of hotel management major students. Also, Mtemeri (2017), Hui, Rashid and Mohammed (2017), Bikse et.al (2018) and Abdinoor and Ibrahim (2019) stated that parents can affect students' intention on career choice.

Career development can affect hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry can be aligned with the researches that being done by Lusby (2017), Hui, Rashida and Mohammed (2017) and Mohammed (2018), as the results from their researches were indicated that good career development opportunities in hospitality industry can be a motivation factors for hospitality students to join hospitality industry. Moreover, according to Ezeuduji and Mbane (2017), El-houshy (2018), Le, Klieve and McDonald (2018) and Wahab, Rosli and Shahril (2020), their researches claimed that career development are one of the main concerns of students while choosing career path.

Not only that, the result of personal interest can affect hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry was aligned with the results that found, as the researchers found that students would join hospitality industry because of personal interest. Not only that, as stated Akosah-Twumasi et al (2018) and Ouano et al (2019), as the researchers claimed that people would choose their career based on their interest. Furthermore, the researcher that done by Atitsogbe et.al (2018), Akosah-Twumasi et al (2018), Malik, Said and Munap (2018) and Adhoch (2019) claimed that personal interest can influence one's career choice.

Limitation

There are several limitations being identified while conducting the research study. First, the limitation of the study would be the time limit. The researcher has only about 10 weeks to finish the research. There are many procedures needed to go through while conducting a research study. From the beginning, the researcher needed to understand about the topic by reviewing many relevant researches. After that, researcher need to come out with a questionnaire in order to collect data. Then, pilot test has been done in order to ensure that there is no problem occurred before going to the actual data collection. Then, the researcher needed to spread out the questionnaire to the target respondents in order to collect sufficient set of valid data for the research. This step required a lot of time as there are more than 150 sets of responses need to be collected. After data collection, data analysis needed to be done too. From my point of view, it would be a bit rush for doing a research study within a short duration.

Secondly, the limitation of the study is the researcher was hard to collect data. In the step of data collection while doing the researcher, Conditional Movement Control Order (CMCO) had started. Hence, students were not allowed going back to campus during the CMCO. It would be difficult for the researcher to reach out the target respondents, which is hospitality students in Berjaya University College. The questionnaire only can be spread out via online included messaging application (Whatsapp), Social Media (Facebook and Instagram) and

The CN. Therefore, it would be difficult to collect responses from the target respondents as some respondents might be hard to reach out.

Not only that, the other limitation that being identified in the study is the sample size and the area that being used to conducted the study. The study only focused on hospitality students who are studying in Berjaya University College. It is because of the COVID-19 outbreak, the researcher worried about the difficulty of data collection from other higher education institutions. Hence, it can be said that this is a really small sample size and area. Therefore, it can be said that this study may not be sufficient enough to be a perfect research as the sample size and area that being covered in the study is very little. This study only represents the working intention towards hospitality industry of hospitality students in Berjaya University College but not represents the working intention of hospitality students from other higher education institutions. Therefore, the research only can be a reference for further research but not to be a perfect research.

Moreover, limited variable is also one of the limitations in the study. There are only four independent variables being conducted in the study. There might be more independent variables can be used in the study. However, due to the time limitation, only four independent variables can be conducted. As the more the variables, the longer time needed to complete the research. Although the limited variable might make the research not to be the perfect as there are only few independent variables being conducted in the research, the researcher was able to finish the research on time by conducting the four independent variables in the research.

Recommendation

Due to several limitations occurred in the study, some recommendations were being discussed by the researcher. First of all, larger sample size and area are recommended to be conducted in the further researches. As this research only focus on hospitality students in Berjaya University College, it is not sufficient to represent all the hospitality student in Kuala Lumpur. Thus, other researchers might consider study the hospitality students' intention from other higher education institution in order to make the research better and deeper. The larger of the sample size and area might make the result of the research to be more reliable.

Furthermore, the researcher recommends other researchers to have longer time for conducting the research. There are many procedures to go through while conducting a research study. Longer duration for conducting the research might can let the researcher to do the research more detailed and deeper. Good thing takes time, same case to a good research study. Longer duration might give the researcher more time to do more researches on the topic, to do more review on other journals, and to conduct more variables in the research. Thus, the researcher would like to say that it is better to have longer time while conducting a research study in order to make the research to be stronger and deeper.

Besides, the researcher recommends that more variables can be conducted in the further researches. As there are only four independent variables being conducted in the study, there might be more possible independent variables can affect hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry. Thus, other researchers can conduct the further study by including more variables and other variables which have not being included in this study such as peer influence and physical working condition in order to understand more about the factor that affecting hospitality students' working intention towards hospitality industry.

Last but not least, the other recommendation would be about the data collection. As the researcher has faced difficulty on the data collection, the researcher recommends that to have both online questionnaire and physical questionnaire if the circumstance is allowing to do so. The researcher think that this would have higher chances to reach out hospitality students while spreading the questionnaire in the campus. Using both online questionnaire and physical questionnaire might can lower the difficulty of collecting data.

To sum up, the study has conducted several variables included pay and benefits, parental influence, career development and personal interest. The study has found that pay and benefits, parental influence, career development and personal interest would affect hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry. Although the study was only focused on hospitality student in Berjaya University College, it might also can help further researcher to conduct relevant research on understanding students' working intention towards hospitality industry.

From this research, this might also can help the employers or Human Resource workers to know the factor to attract hospitality students to join hospitality industry. As all the independent variables in this study can

affect hospitality students' intention towards working in hospitality industry, the employers and Human Resource workers in hospitality industry can enhance those factors, so that the hospitality students' working intention to join hospitality industry would be stronger.

It is essential to attract those ideal workers to work in hospitality industry. The ways might can be used for attracting hospitality students to join hospitality industry:

The employers of hospitality industry can consider to offer attractive pay and benefits for hospitality employees. Strategic income management should be implemented in order to be competitive among other industries. Not only that, the industry should emphasize on having sufficient benefits such as health care and welfare, leave benefits and flexible working time benefits and increasing on salary in order to attract people joining hospitality industry

Training programme might be the important elements to attract hospitality students to join hospitality industry. As stated by Pol and Patil (2015), sufficient amount of learning opportunities should be provided during internship or during working in order for hospitality students to be confident for joining hospitality industry.

Hospitality educators play important role in attracting hospitality students to join hospitality industry. Career guidance of the educators is important in order to let hospitality students know more about the real working industry. Hospitality educators may collaborate with the institution in hospitality industry to have some talks in order to let the hospitality students to understand the advantages of working in hospitality industry and the requirements to work in the industry (Malik, Said and Munap 2018).

As stated by Lusby (2017), hospitality organizations might offer more scholarship opportunities, campus recruitment and information sharing for hospitality students in order to help the hospitality be confident to join hospitality industry. The image and the reputation of the industry should be good in order to stimulate hospitality students' interest and let their parents know that hospitality industry is a good industry to join.

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